

REINFORCED CONCRETE PERFORMANCE SHORT COLUMNS INCORPORATING WITH OLIVE OIL MILL AND BRINE WASTEWATER

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Abstract

Based on previous research [24 – 29], it was found that the ratio that gives us the best strength in reinforced concrete is 7.5 % for olive oil mill wastewater (OOMW) and 10% for brine wastewater (BW). 36 short columns of reinforced concrete measuring 150 mm x 150 mm x 1000 mm were prepared with the addition of 7.5% of OOMW and a ratio of 10% of BW, 12 samples for each ratio, respectively, and 12 Compared RC columns were prepared for comparison, all of the samples were held together with steel that was 10 mm in diameter and stirrups that were 8 mm in diameter, after 7, 14, 21, and 28 days, all samples were looked at, it was found that adding BW lowers the compressive strength of reinforced concrete by 10% and adding OOMW lowers it by 3% at the 28-day edge.

Keywords: Breine Wastewater; Olive Oil Mill Wastewater; Compressive Strength; Columns.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last century and of the current century, there was massive use of reinforced concrete in the construction industry, which was necessary due to development and prosperity in the world because RC is one of the most important building materials and the most important structural elements [1], structural elements, especially columns, may need additional reinforcement to bear the additional loads arising and the increasing demand for the materials and materials techniques used [2], many researchers have used materials such as (CFRP), (GFRP), and others to strengthen columns and other structural elements [3-8].

The problem of neglected waste, especially the one that has a significant impact on the environment resulting from production and development, has become a major problem. Therefore, employing this waste in the production of concrete and RC is considered a strategic factor to manage this waste [9 - 11].

More than a billion tons of water resources have been used to cure concrete mix, therefore the suggested materials would ease the strain on water resources [12, 13], by 2050, over half of the global population will experience water scarcity owing to development; thus, it is essential to assess the influence of human use on water resources [14-18], using saltwater in concrete mixes might affect how strong the concrete is compared to mixtures prepared with fresh water.

However, using saltwater in reinforced concrete around 15 degrees Celsius is typically not a good idea since it could make the rebar rust [19], studies have shown that the negative effects of chloride ions from saltwater on concrete are quite minimal and may be disregarded without fear [20], because of this, researchers are looking into new environmentally friendly and cost-effective ways to handle concrete [21-23].

This research used Olive Oil Mill and Brine Wastewater, both of which are ecologically detrimental wastes, added at concentrations of 7.5% and 10%, respectively. These percentages were chosen based on previous and ongoing research [24-29], as they were determined to be the best percentages when used in the production of reinforced concrete.

In this research, the strength of RC to compression was studied. When using OOMW and BW, a better compressive strength was obtained than when using Dead Sea water [30].

The aim of this research, in addition to its importance from an environmental standpoint, is to know the extent to which the use of BW and OOMW affects the production of RC and how it affects its Compressive Strength.

$$\text{Strength of Compressive} = P/A \tag{1}$$

Were, P – is failure load (KN), A- Cross-sectional Area

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Brine wastewater, olive oil mill effluent, silica sand, and cement - References [24–34] list the physical and chemical needs of silica sand, brine wastewater, olive oil mill effluent, and cement.

Operation of Experiments

This research contains the results of the tests on 36 columns measuring 150 mm x150 mm x 1000 mm of reinforced concrete, were: 12 reference samples without BW and OOMW, 12 samples with Brine wastewater, from each added percentage 10%, and 12 samples with OOMW, from each added percentage 7.5%. When the diameters of the rebars are 10, and 8 respectively, all of the columns are reinforced (Figure 1,2).

As shown in Figure 3, the chart samples from the compressive strength tests of reinforced concrete are shown, steel reinforcement was used in the research as shown in Table 1, also, 36 cubes measuring 150 mm x150 mm were prepared and tested along with the columns at the ages of 7,14,21, in addition to 28 days in order to determine the Compressive strength of the concrete.

Table 1: The results of the steel reinforcement test that were used in the study in order to get at it

Diameter, (mm)	Samples NO.	Length, mm	Tensile Force, (KN)	Average tensile Force, (KN)
10	1	500	108.85	108.61
	2	510	107.43	
	3	505	109.55	
8	1	480	23.7	23.90
	2	481	24.1	
	3	480	23.9	

Figure 1: Column Detailing

Figure 2: The Shape of the Reinforcement of Compressive

Figure 3: Investigations Chart Columns

Production of Concrete with Reinforced Elements

In this study, four fundamental laboratory steps were investigated and worked on, and Cube Manufacturing, Surface Finishing, Moldings, and Removal from the mold, can be referred to in [24-29], the sample processing, curing processes, and Sample Screening Device of Reinforced Concrete Columns are shown in Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7 respectively.

Figure 4: Process of fixing Rebar in the form

Figure 5: Process of Column Manufacturing

Figure 6: Curing Process

Figure 7: Sample Screening Device of Reinforced Concrete Columns

Testing of Specimens

All tests have been performed on all mixtures after 7,14,21,28 days. Concrete compressive strength (MPa) and reinforced concrete compressive strength (KN) with BW and OOMW are shown in Tables (2, and 3).

Table 2: Compressive Strength of Concrete with OOMW and BW For 7, 14, 21, And 28 Days.

The Age (Day)	No Of Series	No Of Cubes	Cubes (mm) 150x150x150	Average Load (Stresses - MPa)		
				Cubes Control Sample	Cubes with BW (10 %)	Cubes with OOMW (7.5%)
7	I	1	Cc-1	21.80	24.93	26.10
			Cco -1			
			CcB -1			
		2	Cc-2			
			Cco-2			
			CcB-2			
		3	Cc-3			
			Cco-3			
			CcB-3			

14	II	1	Cc-1	25.52	27.96	30.95
			Cco -1			
			CcB -1			
		2	Cc-2			
			Cco-2			
			CcB-2			
		3	Cc-3			
			Cco-3			
			CcB-3			
21	III	1	Cc-1	28.38	32.99	36.44
			Cco -1			
			CcB -1			
		2	Cc-2			
			Cco-2			
			CcB-2			
		3	Cc-3			
			Cco-3			
			CcB-3			
28	IV	1	Cc-1	29.84	35.14	38.44
			Cco -1			
			CcB -1			
		2	Cc-2			
			Cco-2			
			CcB-2			
		3	Cc-3			
			Cco-3			
			CcB-3			
Cc - Cubes without olive oil mill and brine wastewater Cco -Cubes with olive oil mill wastewater CcB – Cubes with Brine wastewater						

Table 3: Reinforced Concrete Compressive Strength with OOMW and BW For 7, 14, 21 And 28 Days

The Age (Day)	No Of Series	No Of Columns	Columns (mm) 150x150x1000	Average Load (KN)		
				Control Sample	Column With OOW (7.5 %)	Column With BW (% 10)
7	I	1	c-1	416.39	446.25	420.87
			co -1			
			cB -1			
		2	c-2			
			co-2			
			cB-2			
		3	c-3			
			co-3			
			cB-3			
		1	c-1			
			co -1			
			cB-1			
		2	c-2			

14	II	3	co-2	520.60	505.78	440.43
			cB-2			
			c-3			
			co-3			
			cB-3			
21	III	1	c-1	563.11	550.42	499.91
			co -1			
			cB-1			
		2	c-2			
			co-2			
			cB-2			
		3	c-3			
			Rco-3			
			cB-3			
28	IV	1	c-1	612.61	594.47	550.29
			co -1			
			cB-1			
		2	c-2			
			co-2			
			cB-2			
		3	c-3			
			co-3			
			cB-3			
c- Column Without Olive Oil Mill and Brine Wastewater co -Column with Olive Oil Mill Wastewater cB - Column with Brine Wastewater						

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After completing the laboratory work and obtaining the results of the tests Table (2, 3), we include. The following analysis and discussion of these results, as follows:

Compressive strength for Concrete cubes.

The compressive strength of concrete is determined by a number of parameters, such as its age, the amount of cement it contains, the ratio of water to cement, and the ratio of over-water to cement, BW-to-cement ratio, OOMW-to-cement ratio, processing, additives, and other factors. All samples that had both olive oil mill and brine effluent on them had harder surfaces than those that had just fresh water on them, the failure modes of the cubes with OOMW and BW, like its regular concrete analogs known to us, all samples are tested after 7,14, 21, and 28 days. As is known to us from previous studies [24-29] and has been proven in this research, the best percentage of OOMW that gave the highest compressive strength was 7.5 %, and it was 38.44 MPa after 28 days, which is better than regular concrete by a percentage equal to 29 %, and the best percentage of BW that gave the highest compressive strength was 10 %, and it was 35.14 MPa after 28 days, which is better than regular concrete by a percentage equal to 18 %, as is clear that adding OOMW and BW from a ratio of 7.5% in OOMW increases the compressive strength by (20 – 29) %, and a ratio of 10% BW increases the compressive strength by (10 - 18) % in shortage. In general, the compressive stress curves for the age of concrete with OOMW and BW added are like the curves of conventional concrete, (Table 2, and Figure 8), The failure mode of the cubes is the same as in previous studies (24-29).

Figure 8: Concrete Compressive Strength

Axial Behavior of RC Columns

The compressive strength of reinforced concrete is influenced by several factors, including its age, cement content, water-to-cement ratio, OOMW-to-cement ratio, BW-to-cement ratio, curing method, type of reinforcement, and more elements.

Figure 9: Failure Modes of the Column (control Samples)

Figure 10: Failure Modes of the Column: a. With OOW, and b. With BW

Figures 9 and 10 indicate how the columns that were looked at failed, at the top of the columns, concrete crushing occurs, and it spreads down toward the middle of the column (Figure 9), the modes failure of columns with OOW is like the failure modes of compared columns (figure 10.a.), as for failure modes in columns that contain BW, it was generally the result of the concrete breaking apart from the longitudinal steel of the column to the middle, and in a few samples, the concrete crushing near the top of the columns (figure 10. b), the buckling of the longitudinal steel was found after the concrete cover spalled off, even though the buckling in the columns with BW and OOW is less than what is in the compared samples.

Figure 11: Reinforced Concrete Compressive Strength

The compressive strength values of RC columns with BW and OOW at the curing age of 7,14,21 and 28 days are shown in (Figure 11 and Table 3). The ultimate compressive strength of the control samples was recorded as 612.61 KN, 594.47 KN in the columns with OOW, and 550.04 KN in the columns with BW, at the point of fracture. That is, adding OOW reduces the compressive strength of the columns by (2 -3) % while adding BW reduces the compressive strength of the columns by (10-15) % in shortage. But for up to 7 days, the addition of BW and OOW gives us a higher compressive strength by (1-7) %, and this is due to the crystallization process resulting from the salt substance,

which is one of the components. If we look at Table 2, we conclude that the concrete compressive strength with BW and OOMW is highest in the reference samples, but of RC columns compressive strength that contains BW and OOMW must be less than the reference columns (Figure 11), the reason lies in the ratio of the high salt content in BW and OOMW which hinders good bond strength between the steel reinforcement and the concrete, causing rapid failure of the columns when loaded axially.

Table 4: Results of the test columns in 28 Days

NO. of Columns	Maximum Load (KN)	Displacement	Failure Mode
C-1	600.00	0.93	Buckling
C-2	564.34	0.86	Crushing
C-3	673.47	1.02	Buckling
CO-1	596.32	0.34	Crushing
CO-2	585.50	0.38	Crushing
CO-3	601.60	0.41	Crushing
CB-1	539.51	0.36	Crushing
CB-2	560.58	0.42	Crushing
CB-3	550.04	0.32	Crushing

A. Control Samples

B. With OOMW

C. With BW

Figure 12: Load-deformation behavior of the columns in 28 days: a control samples, B. With olive oil mill Wastewater, c. With Brine Wastewater

The load-displacement curves are provided in (figure 12) obtained from experiment testing of the columns providing valuable value insights into their behavioral response in 28 days. The control column C- 1, C- 2, C- 3 (Figure 12. a), which was strengthened, displayed an approximately linear Load-displacement relationship from zero loading up to reaching its maximum load capacity, after which sudden brittle failure occurred in contrast, all of the columns with BW and OOMW specimens exhibited enhanced load – bearing compared to the control samples. However, the columns obtained BW CB-1, CB-2, CB-3 (Figure 12. b), and OOMW Co-1, Co-2, and Co-3 (Figure 12. c), also failed in less softness, in post-peak load, and demonstrated substantially greater ductility, and deflection values, similar to compared columns, adding BW and OOMW lowers the displacement a lot, as seen by the displacement curves. This is because salat, one of the materials' components, is what makes the crystals form. As seen above, adding BW and OOMW lowers the compressive strength of the reinforced concrete since the rebar and concrete don't stick together well, the design moment should be the maximum moment times the coefficient (η), this is the number you should use. There is a coefficient denoted by the symbol (η) that is used to reflect the decrease in the strength of the columns when the bond levels are lower., you may get the updated value of it in the equation [26, 27]. Many research has looked at how treated wastewater may be used, however as was said before, saline wastewater is not used to make reinforced concrete or to test its bending or compressive strength, even though this water didn't have the same physical and chemical properties as saline wastewater, its bending and compression strength remained the same, adding materials to both mounds made the bending strength go up by 2 to 5 percent. This approach is used to find the design axial load (P_n), design shear strength (V_n), and design bending strength (M_n) of a number of the strongest materials, the values of the coefficients depend on what the code says about strength and failure reasons (ACI Table 21.2.1), when looking at the table, it is clear that the tensile failure of the components that are subjected to either an axial force or both is governed by the tensile failure it is ($\Phi = 0.65$), which is relevant to the tests that we have conducted for this research, it is recommended that the design strength be higher than or equal to the design forces in the majority of conditions.

$$Mu \leq \Phi P_n \quad (2)$$

As a result, it is essential that the nominal strength surpasses the needed strength by a margin that is equivalent to one-fourth of the angular value, or at least that:

$$M_n \geq P_u / \Phi \quad (3)$$

Henceforth, the parameter Φ is crucial for design purposes, we might suggest a coefficient of (η) as a substitute for the coefficient of (Φ) based on the few studies that have been done so far in this study and research [24, 26], we did this because we thought about how strong the relationship is between rebar and concrete, even when the concrete is mixed with saline and olive oil mill wastewaters, we also made sure that all the relevant safety precautions are taken into account, for example, you may take it from [24, 26] when using reinforced concrete with diameters of 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, and 16.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is possible that we will arrive to the following findings after carrying out tests, assessing the results, and carefully studying the data:

1. The compressive strength of concrete with a combination of BW and OOMW, high compressive strength of regular concrete by 18%, and 29% respectively, as demonstrated [24 - 28].
2. Compressive strength is reduced by 3% and 10%, respectively, when OOMW and BW are added to the compensation of RC, this results in a reduction of the average compressive strength.
3. Incorporating BW and OOMW into RC enhanced its strength and reduced the likelihood of buckling.
4. His study and other studies [24–28] have shown that including 7.5 % OOMW and 10% BW does not substantially compromise RC, we can confidently use this novel concrete in the highway reinforced slab, a substantial ground slab in the parking lot, an extensive basement storage space, and a non-residential structure.
5. To improve understanding of the effects of integrating brine and olive oil mill effluent on the components of reinforced concrete, we suggest examining reinforced concrete samples for compression, bending, and torsion at extended ages.

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